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Narrative Review of Research on Youthreach

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Summary Report:

- Need for the provision of literacy and numeracy in Youthreach and Post compulsory settings to be rooted in the subjective context of learner's lives.
- Need for acknowledgement of new approaches to literacy and numeracy teaching that are not tied to funding lines and metrics.
- Suggestion that literacy programmes should not be linked to student numbers and metrics as it can stigmatise and encourage disengagement.
- Acknowledgement of the success of literacy and numeracy approaches that take cultural, gendered and contextual experiences into consideration.
- Acknowledgement of the need to engage with learners in a social and collaborative approach that allows young people to also learn from each other.
- Suggestion that authentic materials and multi-modal approaches be used to engage young people.
- Recognition that literacy and numeracy approaches need to be embedded in lifelong learning approaches through compulsory education and vocational and adult education settings.
- Suggestions that maths can be used for the development of self-determination skills for young adults with support needs.

Recommendations:

Recommendation 1: Social policy should form the context of specific educational policy on literacy and numeracy that addresses social and economic issues that impact on school engagement and completion (Borgna, 2017) Enabling parents and communities.

Recommendation 2: Literacy and numeracy approaches be embedded in a 'personalised, pastorally underpinned educational provision' (Smith & Wright, 2015) (Curriculum and the learning experience).

Recommendation 3: Literacy and numeracy approaches should be responsive to the cultural, gendered and social context of the learner (Eglash et al., 2013) (Curriculum and the learning experience).

Recommendation 4: Access to literacy and numeracy should underpin all educational provision in post compulsory education including vocational settings (Lechner et al., 2021) (Curriculum and the learning experience).

Recommendation 5: Consistent access to literacy and numeracy supports that provide appropriate teaching and learning strategies should be available through the lifespan to improve outcomes for young adults with educational disabilities (Moni et al., 2018). (Students with Additional Learning Needs).

Overview

This section focuses on literacy, numeracy and digital literacy in Youthreach settings. While this section is focused on literacy and numeracy, a broader approach is taken to reflect the wider age cohort of post compulsory education and early school leaving across other settings and jurisdictions. The intention is to display the array of approaches utilised in school settings and post compulsory settings that aim to address cultural and generational issues in the age range of young adults served by the Youthreach programme. Where relevant, additional research on teaching literacy, numeracy and mathematics in the young adult population has been included to contextualise a varied and diverse young adult demographic.

A systematic literature review was carried out in academic databases that found a lack of systematic literature reviews on the specific topic of literacy, numeracy and digital literacy in Youthreach settings. This may be due to the purpose of the Youthreach programme as a ‘second chance’ education programme for early school leavers and the holistic focus on soft skills for young adults who have left the mainstream compulsory second level school system. Much of the research carried out in Youthreach is contained in Masters Theses and government reports that highlight the issue of learners entering Youthreach Centres with low levels of literacy and numeracy. Youthreach staff as part of the ESRI Youthreach Evaluation Report acknowledge the variation in levels of literacy and numeracy in learners entering Youthreach from compulsory education settings. They note that the level and type of literacy challenges vary in each learner depending on their subjective experience of school (ESRI, 2019).

The Youthreach programme was established in 1989 and is the government’s primary response to early school leaving in Ireland. Its aim is to provide second-chance education for young people aged 15-20 who leave mainstream second level school before Leaving Certificate (ESRI, 2019). Youthreach is provided in 112 Youthreach centres and 35 Community Training Centres (CTCs) nationally, with 11,104 learners taking part in the programme in 2017 and with a total cost of €98.7 million (SOLAS, 2018). Youthreach Centres are designated as ‘centres of education’ under the Education Act 1998 and are managed and administered by ETBs. CTCs are set up by local community organisations and have their own board of management although funded by the ETB under annual submission (ESRI, 2019). The majority of centres offer QQI Levels 3 and 4 qualifications, with a fifth offering QQI Level 2 courses or the Leaving Certificate Applied programme, and under a tenth providing the Junior Certificate or Leaving Certificate Established.

Research Questions

- What strategies or approaches support the literacy needs of students in Youthreach Centres and/or post compulsory settings?
- What practices and tools facilitate literacy learning in Youthreach Centres?
- What strategies or approaches support the numeracy needs of students in Youthreach Centres and/or post compulsory settings?
- What practices and tools facilitate numeracy in Youthreach Centres?
- What strategies or approaches support the digital literacy needs of students in Youthreach Centres and/or post compulsory settings?
- What practices and tools facilitate digital literacy in Youthreach Centres or post-compulsory settings?

Key Search Terms

(learners in Youthreach OR early school leavers OR post compulsory education) AND ("literacy" OR "writing" OR "reading skills" OR "literacy assistance" OR "learning support") AND ("systematic review" OR review OR "best evidence" OR "meta-analysis" OR "literature review") AND (literacy OR numeracy OR "digital literacy")

(learners in Youthreach OR early school leavers OR post compulsory education) AND ("numeracy" OR "numbers" OR "mathematics" OR "mathematical reasoning" OR "learning support") AND ("systematic review" OR review OR "best evidence" OR "meta-analysis" OR "literature review") AND (literacy OR numeracy OR "digital literacy")

(learners in Youthreach OR early school leavers OR post compulsory education) AND ("digital literacy" OR "computers" OR "technology skills" OR "digital skills" OR "learning support") AND ("systematic review" OR review OR "best evidence" OR "meta-analysis" OR "literature review") AND (literacy OR numeracy OR "digital literacy")

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Accessible in English
- Published in any country
- Published in a peer reviewed academic journal
- Refers to literacy, numeracy or digital literacy
- Refers to Youthreach Programme and/or early school leavers and/or post compulsory settings and/or young adults
- Refers to literacy practices or strategies
- Refers to different types of approaches in post-compulsory education

Exclusion criteria

- Published prior to 2011
- Published in a non peer reviewed academic journal

Note: Due to the specific focus and nature of Youthreach in Ireland, strategies and approaches to literacy, numeracy and digital literacy in post compulsory education and in a range of settings including adult and special educational needs were not excluded.

Key Data Sources Consulted

Databases consulted

- Academic Search Complete
- Education Research Complete
- EBSCO
- ERIC International
- Google Scholar
- SCOPUS

Other sources consulted

- Masters Theses on the Youthreach Programme
- 'Grey literature' (reports published by international and national organisations/governments)

Key definitions:

“Leander and Boldt (2013) described literacy activity as not primarily about generating signs of meanings as end points, but rather as ‘generating intensity and the excitement of emergence’ (p. 26), where literacy is understood within material, embodied, relational, and semiotic assemblages” (Burnett & Merchant, 2018; Leander & Boldt, 2013 cited in Comber & Carter, 2019).

“Current thinking on numeracy points to the need to account for contemporary understandings of adult numeracy by giving more attention to: dispositions to use mathematics; the ability to see mathematics in a numeracy situation; critical reflection and action; the degree of accuracy required to solve numeracy problems in context; and digital and technological representations and tools” (Tout et al., 2017 cited in NALA, 2021).

“Literacy is one of the key skills required for navigating a modern technological world, as both literally and figuratively it unlocks the keys to participation and access to all aspects of society including employment” (Dukes & Ming, 2014; McClure, Sinclair, & Aird, 2015 cited in Moni, Joblin & Baffour, 2018).

Ivanic et al. (2007) explain New Literacy Studies (NLS) as “offer[ing] a socially situated and constructed view of literacies as multiple, emergent and situated in particular contexts” (cited in Smith & Wright, 2015).

Narrative

The Youthreach Programme is an unique initiative in Ireland that has facilitated the progression of young people and their self-awareness of their own potential for over three decades. “Both senior managers and centre coordinators or managers see the Youthreach programme as having multiple aims, including re-engaging young people in learning, providing a positive learning experience, and fostering the development of personal and social skills, the acquisition of qualifications, and progression to education, training, and employment” (McCoy, 2019).

The comprehensive evaluation of the Youthreach programme (Smyth et al., 2019) carried out by the Economic Social Research Institute (ESRI) suggested improvements in support for literacy and numeracy, health education and in the implementation of individualised learning plans for learners. It points out that there are a significant number of young Travellers access the programme, many of them with very low levels of literacy and numeracy skills. The report which draws on extensive verbatim evidence from Youthreach staff states that almost all Youthreach Centres used a combination of individual (one-to-one) and small group support from centre staff for young people with literacy and/or numeracy difficulties. Other forms of support included “designated staff or class periods, online learning using Level 2 NALA Write-on and broader support from the advocate or counsellor”. It was also noted that “in six-in-ten cases, centres drew on specialist support in the form of Education and Training Board (ETB) literacy tutors or cooperation hours”. This approach is much more common in Community Training Centre (CTC) settings.

The qualitative interviews with learners highlighted specific difficulties with academic coursework in school such as mathematics and Irish. Learners felt that there was not enough support available to them in school from teachers. A number of learners felt that they were ignored and left on their own. There was a nuanced view from some learners that the way that subjects are taught are geared towards points and college and not towards a practical -based approach that would suit their needs and abilities. The lack of experiential learning or discussion based learning was a challenge for some as the focus was perceived to be primarily academic with a focus on books and a didactic way of teaching.

Earlier research highlighted in the ESRI report displays a sharp increase in “the range of difficulties and issues prevalent among Youthreach learners, with many learners coming from dysfunctional family backgrounds, requiring psychological support and experiencing literacy and numeracy” (McHugh, 2014). Earlier studies by WRC Social and Economic Consultants for the Equality Authority in 2007 found that “50 per cent of young people were from dysfunctional family backgrounds, 30 per cent had literacy and numeracy difficulties and 30 per cent needed psychological support” (WRC Social and Economic Consultants, 2007). The ESRI evaluation quotes one manager who refers to the impact of disengagement from the education system and “the issues around numeracy and literacy for these young people are impacting on their ability to complete QQI Levels 3 and 4” (p.77).

Literacy and Post Compulsory Education

The following research articles highlight the relationship between policy, structures and their impact on the experience of young people who disengage from compulsory education. There is a broad view that a system that presents literacy in a particular model tied to funding, didactic teaching strategies and a mono-cultural approach can limit the people working in the system and the young people in their learning, applying and enjoyment of literacy activities.

Smith & Wright (2015) present a study into literacy education for young people identified as not in education, employment or training (NEETs) who were attending courses with further education (FE) providers in the UK. The data was provided through the viewpoints of 13 adult educators. The authors distinguish between two opposing definitions of literacy: an ‘autonomous’ model and one that is ‘socially situated’. Ivanic et al. (2007, 705) explain New Literacy Studies (NLS) as ‘offer[ing] a socially situated and constructed view of literacies as multiple, emergent and situated in particular contexts’. The authors contend that the autonomous model in the UK connects with a policy agenda that insists that a prescribed level of Standard English “is necessary for young people ‘to thrive in today’s rapidly changing economy’ (DCSF, 2010, p.3). The authors feel that this model of literacy is a “norm that contributes to a structure of exclusion and inclusion”.

Gee (2000, p.180) describes New Literacy Studies as “based on the view that reading and writing only make sense when studied in the context of social and cultural practices of which

they are but a part”. The research acknowledges that students “may be digitally literate in particular ways e.g. digitally literate though they may struggle in other areas such as academic writing”. The authors point that literacy courses may be regarded with ‘suspicion’ by students who feel that participating in such courses brand them as ‘stupid’. The research findings suggest that literacy provision that “objectifies students in order to maximise success rates exacerbates the disengagement that is already a feature of these student’s personal histories”. The structural provision of such courses in the UK that operate in an FET environment where student retention and qualification within a specified timeframe is tied to funding inhibits the “personalised, pastorally underpinned educational provision that this group of students requires”.

Borgna (2017) explores the social stratification of literacy skills among young adults through the analysis of data from the 2011/2012 Programme for International Assessment of Adult Competences (PIAAC) and post compulsory education across 18 OECD countries. “On one hand, in knowledge-based economies, literacy skills are central to ensure employability and their generality makes them widely applicable across working contexts ([Estevez-Abe et al., 2001](#)). On the other hand, literacy is also increasingly valuable in itself in what has been described as ‘the schooled society’ ([Baker, 2014b](#)): in this perspective, failing to attain a basic literacy level is a new social risk and educational policies need to ensure equal chances of skill development for all” ([Allmendinger and Leibfried, 2003](#)). The article finds that educational policies cannot replace compensatory social policies. Secondly, the authors point out the importance of a life course approach to education as social policy.

An Australian study (Polidano et al., 2015) examined re-engagement patterns in early school leavers up to six years after leaving school where most youth in the sample of 37,800 students were aged 21.4 . The study found “no evidence that school factors associated with increased chances of completing school, such as higher numeracy and literacy levels, increased years of retention, and positive attitudes to school are associated with increased chances of re-engaging early school leavers”. Instead this study demonstrates the contribution of a highly accessible VET system in promoting equity of opportunity among early school leavers, regardless of past academic performance. Findings suggest that careers in VET are attractive to early school’s leavers as they focus on practical hands on experience as opposed to theory. The study also emphasises the need for early access to career counselling for all students as most career counselling is provided at upper secondary level when many students

have already left school.

The following articles indicate that specific educational policies in compulsory education must be contextualised in an approach that responds to a variety of life progressions and be part of a social policy that includes literacy education within a socially contextualised progression route. The construction of tests that influence national policies are also key to how we understand the teaching of literacy in gendered and fast moving societies

A study of the review of data from the PSIA and PIAAC surveys across Nordic countries (Solheim & Lundetrae, 2018) demonstrates patterns of gender difference in the target age groups of 10 year olds in PIRLS (15) (2011), 15 year olds in PISA (2009) and PIAAC (2012). Their finding of changing gender differences by age group and survey could be interpreted in at least four ways (1) PIAAC is more boy friendly and masks real gender differences; or (2) PISA has a girl friendly design and does not give a correct picture of boys reading skills; or (3) the surveys measure different skills; or (4) gender differences in literacy increase from the age of 10 to the age of fifteen but then disappear with advancing age. These findings relate to the “social and cultural constructions of gender [which] might well influence literacy engagement and hence literacy achievement, as girls and boys may encounter different expectations in their environment (Li, 2011) and “both constructions of literacy and pursuits likely to enhance literacy achievement are often feminised” (Watson, Kehler & Martino, 2010).

In their review of the level of adolescent literacy in Europe, Sulkunen (2013) points out that “many adolescents may still have problems with basic reading skills at the age of 15, as shown for instance in Swedish and Danish studies on PISA students (Skolverket, 2001; Arnbak & Mejding, 2010)”. Despite this, in several European countries the range of reading comprehension strategies in teaching reading literacy is reduced from primary to secondary level although combining several strategies would be the most effective (Eurydice, 2011). It is suggested that literacy should be seen as a larger concept from the point of view of situated use of a complex set of competencies (Coiro et al, 2008), using and producing multimodal texts, printed and digital, and be aware that the content and the linguistic choices in any text are ideological and context dependent (Eggins, 2004; Halliday & Hasan, 1985). The idea is to “use authentic reading materials as an entry point to literacy in familiarising students - especially adolescent struggling readers - with texts that are new to them and challenge them

further to develop their literacy” (Sulkunen, 2007b).

Lechner et al. (2021) examining stability and change in adults’ literacy and numeracy skills, acknowledges that literacy and numeracy are quintessential skills for the welfare and well-being of individuals and societies. The authors define literacy as the ability to understand, use and interpret written text, and numeracy as the ability to access, use and interpret mathematical information. They emphasise that levels of literacy and numeracy are linked to individual-level outcomes such as income, health, and social participation as well as macro-level outcomes such as economic growth (Hanushek et al., 2015; Hanushek & Woessmann, 2015; OECD, 2016). Their findings suggest that adults’ literacy and numeracy are malleable throughout adulthood and can change even over a three-to six-year period. They suggest that these potential losses in skills over time might explain why findings from PIAAC and LEO find “adults with low competences despite...9 or more years of schooling or vocational qualifications” (Durda et al., 2020; Grotluschen et al., 2016, 2020).

Lechner et al. (2021) further point out another perspective from research on adult learning is Practice Engagement Theory [PET; Reder, 1994]. PET originates from literacy research but applies equally to numeracy (Reder et al., 2020). It posits that individuals’ literacy skills “develop as a by-product of their engagement in everyday reading and writing practices. In turn, literacy skills affect levels of engagement in reading and writing practices. PET would predict that adults can experience both gains and losses in literacy and numeracy skills over time—”depending on the extent to which they engage in attendant practices in their job, leisure, or other contexts”. These effects of selection and socialisation have long lasting effects. “For example, those with higher skills as children will, on average, attain higher educational qualifications than those with lower skills, which in turn channels them into more complex jobs that foster the further development of skills”. The authors findings suggest that “literacy and numeracy skills are not “set like plaster” in adulthood and, notwithstanding their strong heritability, show lifelong plasticity”.

Alternative literacy approaches

There was a lack of research found on the literacy and numeracy strategies used within the Youthreach programme. These articles from Ireland, Australia and US illustrate a variety of teaching and learning approaches used in literacy that aim to respond to the needs of diverse

youth in post compulsory settings.

The Funds of Knowledge (FoK) (Moll et al, 1992) and Funds of Pedagogy (FoP) (Rodriguez 2013; Zipin 2009) approach to teaching and learning emphasises the use of knowledge and skills inherent in households, communities, cultures and backgrounds, gathered through ethnographic methods where developmental and process-based approaches to school are emphasised (González, Moll, and Amanti, 2006). Findings from the Adolescent literacy, Identity and School (ALIAS) study showed that teachers in voluntary education settings and Youthreach centres tended to support textual engagement orally and visually in order to prioritise learning without the printed word presenting too much of a barrier for the learners. They scaffolded accessible learning opportunities through visual cues and through creating spaces for oral engagement in their classrooms (Cahill et al., 2020).

Research in an Australian setting on a filmmaking course offered to young people (Comber & Carter, 2019) examined the literacy approaches used in post compulsory or pre-employment settings. They point out that “literacy is often ambivalently situated in transitional education between school and work, held up as an essential skill, as personal and cultural enrichment, or as somewhere along such a scale”. A multi-literacies pedagogies approach was explored with six young people through a community based youth agency that supports young people in gaining employment or entering FET. The course embedded literacy practices challenged atomistic and mechanical approaches that focus narrowly on work related literacies performed by individuals. Rather literacy practices happened within relational processes working with and through shared experiences. The authors explained that “For the young people in this course, dialogic pedagogies and storytelling provided opportunities for imagining something new, including how they could talk about their own futures” (Comber & Carter, 2019).

A project focusing on public school adolescents in the US (Zenkov, Taylor & Harmon, 2015) recognised that many children of ‘multiple generations of high school dropouts or pushouts’ had a tenuous appreciation of English instruction (Chapman, Laird, Ifill & KewalRamani, 2011). This project uses literacy instruction methods that rely on expanded notions of text, including a photovoice approach and digital photographs, [which] have proven to be effective for engaging diverse youths (Ewald, 2011). Interestingly this project also engages a literacy development approach that is rooted in empowerment and the ‘Freirean concept of linking

the word and the world'. By using imagery as a language through which the young people can illustrate their perspectives the authors assume that young people 'are experts on these phenomena, that they should be treated as authorities on their relationships to literacy and that they should inform the curricula and pedagogies that teachers use' (Biddulph, 2011; Cook-Sather, 2009). The authors emphasise the need for a developmental orientation to the writing growth of young people which includes a 'reliance on young people collaborating with one another' and being the audience for each other's writing.

Teaching Mathematics

In the absence of research particularly focusing on numeracy in post-compulsory settings, the following research articles refer to the impact of self-fulfilling prophecies in urban after school contexts in the US and the influence of culture on young people's motivation and ambition. This type of research may have relevance to stratified groups in Irish society who are grouped under socio economic designations or minority groups such as the Traveller Community. These influences can be hidden in the media that young people consume such as young adult literature where a negative view of mathematics can be subtly presented. Tout (2020) explores numeracy as a social practice related to the context of the problem but ultimately leading to the workplace.

A report on culturally responsive computing in urban after school contexts in North America (Eglash et al., 2013) makes an interesting point about self-fulfilling prophecies: "Like the myth of cultural determinism, the myth of genetic determinism becomes a self-fulfilling prophecy: If you believe you are predestined to do poorly in math, there is no point in trying, and your math grades will indeed be lower as predicted. With lower expectations from students and teachers, test anxiety from stereotype threat, and excuses for poor performance that can act as a badge of honor ("at least I'm not a sell-out"), these myths generate serious barriers to academic performance". The article highlights that in culture based math instruction, teachers and students use more active approaches such as inquiry learning. This inductive approach provides additional social dimensions (Vygotsky, 1978). The authors point out that there are limits to this discovery learning method due to learner frustration if under prepared, the potential for misconceptions to be reinforced and the difficulty in mastering some "without considerable repetition" (Kirschner, Sweller, & Clark, 2006). The authors suggest that children have become adept and more used to using "passive deductive

pedagogy” such as sophisticated video and/or animation (Ito et al., 2010). The article examines the influence of culture on the “attention machinery” people use for difficult cognitive tasks and references “Ethno-mathematics” which explores mathematical practices embedded in cultural activities.

In a US study on young adult texts and the mathematics stereotypes depicted within, findings demonstrated that over half of the texts studied presented a negative view of subject (n=31), followed by neutral (n=17), positive (n=7) and mixed (n=4). Darragh (2018) focused her analysis on 59 YA novels referencing the mathematics classroom and found that: “it signifies the message that mathematics class is a place where tension is created, where teachers are unfavorable or patently cruel, where meaning and connection cannot exist—one in which math teachers are portrayed negatively and where the learning and doing of mathematics is considered a nerve-wracking chore and open only to geniuses who happen to be predominantly white and able-bodied”. The authors point out that current tropes associated with school mathematics need to be confronted and challenged to allow all students “to own, do and see themselves as mathematicians” (Rezvi et al., 2020).

Tout (2020) examines the evolution of adult numeracy from quantitative literacy to numeracy through the examination of international assessments in the International Adult Literacy Survey (1990s), the Adult Literacy and Lifeskills Survey (mid-2000s) and PIAAC (2009). “Numeracy as a social practice relates to the use of mathematics within a context defined not just by the problem, but also by the physical and social context in which it is situated”. One of the key outcomes of research into the demand for “techno-mathematical literacy skills (Hoyles et al., 2010) in 21st century workplaces” is the ability to understand and reflect on the interaction of these new skills with technology and digital environments. These interactions require people to apply more than basic competency and skills from numeracy related tasks to the workplace but rather entail a “more sophisticated mathematical problem solving skill and understanding to engage with mathematics in a ‘messy’ workplace setting”. It is pointed out that “digital tools increasingly mediate young workers’ ways of reasoning, acting and working (Zevenbergen 2004; Jorgensen 2011).

Digital Literacies

The following articles illustrate positive experiences of Youthreach students using

computerised programmes but the UK research warns of moves in systemic provision of computer education that can inhibit engagement. The study examining the use of computers in a mental health context in Youthreach found that students felt confident using the computer within a supported setting. The findings acknowledged the low levels of literacy among Youthreach students and the need for the programme “to be able to grab the attention of the young person from the start by being visually attractive, easy to follow, and activity based”. McFarlane (2019) emphasises the importance of basic literacy and numeracy as part of the move into digital competence and suggests that the systemic interventions in the UK have not had the expected impact on young people and their interaction with digital education.

A study exploring the use of computerised mental health programmes in alternative education with 38 Youthreach students (Kuosmanen, Fleming & Barry, 2018) found that the majority of students reported feeling very confident (54%) or confident (38%) using a computer. The programme focusing on the use of cognitive behavioural therapies in mental health approaches acknowledges “low levels of literacy among Youthreach students”. Findings show that technology-related barriers included computer literacy difficulties for some students, the lack of face-to-face interaction posing challenges for staff in terms of monitoring adverse reactions, and the view that students appear to work better when hands-on support and opportunities for discussion are provided. Four overall values were elicited from staff discussions relating to program implementation: “planning and timetabling complemented by face-to-face support, flexibility in delivery, and supporting the role and functioning of the Centre”.

In a UK paper examining the “Competing Visions of a good education in the digital age” (McFarlane, 2019) points out that the OECD’s analysis of the wider PISA results found that “basic literacy and numeracy also remain vital to the development of digital competence and may in the long run be more important than general digital experience”. The authors emphasise that the move from ICT to Computing in 2013 in the GCSE curriculum suggests that the numbers taking any aspect of computing at GSCE level is static but that the gender balance in computing compared to ICT has dropped female participation from 39% to 20%. The authors suggest that “the drive to increase specialist knowledge for all has resulted in less general knowledge for all”.

Literacy for young adults with disabilities or additional needs

The following articles have been included to illustrate the need for ongoing literacy and numeracy education for young adults with disabilities. Young adults who join Youthreach can be masking learning difficulties, unassessed neurodiversity and exhibiting behaviours as an outcome of Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs). Gordon (2013) in her Youthreach SEN Initiative Research Report indicates that “the incidence of disability in Youthreach is estimated to be significantly higher than in mainstream schools, particularly in the areas of specific or mild general learning difficulties (Smith, 2002) and emotional and behavioural difficulties (Gordon, 2009)”.

The article examines a programme that aimed to “deliver an evidence-based literacy program to provide opportunities for adults with an intellectual disability aged 18-26 to continue their literacy development in a postsecondary school environment, leading to development of a broad range of literacy skills, self-confidence, independence, and enhanced employment opportunities”. This research provides evidence that when young adults with intellectual disabilities continue literacy education in programs that use appropriate teaching and learning strategies, they continue to develop their literacy (Alfassi, Weiss, & Lifshitz, 2009; Lundberg & Reichenberg, 2013; Reichenberg, 2013). The literacy elements of lifelong learning programmes and inputs need to remain as they are “an essential element in access to vocational pathways and enhance quality of life” (Moni et al., 2018).

This article has explored the use of maths for the development of self-determination skills for young adults with extensive support needs (Gilley et al., 2021). The study took place in a postsecondary transition programme for students with disabilities that served students aged 16 to 22 in the US. The authors contend that mathematical problem solving is a natural context for teaching two component skills of self-determination: self-monitoring and goal setting. In this study “Three young adults with extensive support needs (i.e., autism and intellectual disability) were taught to solve real-world thematic word problems using modified schema-based instruction (MSBI)”. Root et al. (2018) pointed out a shift towards contextualised mathematics for students with SEN by “developing academic skills within relevant real world contexts”. To build self-determination skills, participants self-monitored completion of problem-solving steps using a task analysis, self-graphed steps completed independently correct and then set goals for subsequent sessions within a specific context e.g. cooking. “Practitioners should consider providing students with written or pictorial task

analyses such as the one used in this study and teach students to self-monitor both task completion and level of assistance needed”. The aim and approach of this study aligns with the recommendations of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) approaches (CAST, 2018) in terms of presenting young adults with disabilities opportunities to self-monitor and set goals for themselves.

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